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EDITORIAL NOTE

It is with immense pleasure and pride that we present to you the third issue of the Bauchi State University (BASUG) Law Journal, marking our second publication for the year. This issue stands as a testament to the tireless commitment of our contributors, whose scholarly work continues to push the boundaries of legal scholarship in Nigeria and beyond.

We are particularly elated by the diversity and depth of the submissions received for this edition, not only from across Nigeria but also from international scholars. The topics covered reflect the evolving and multifaceted nature of legal discourse in our contemporary society.

These papers, among others, cover a vast range of legal fields, reflecting the dynamic interplay between law and society. We believe the breadth of scholarship featured in this issue will contribute meaningfully to academic discourse and legal practice.

We would like to extend our profound appreciation to the Faculty of Law, Sa'adu Zungur University, for their unwavering support as our publisher. Our sincere gratitude also goes to the Management of Sa'adu Zungur University for their continued encouragement and partnership in ensuring the success of this journal.

We are deeply indebted to the contributing authors for their invaluable research and dedication to advancing legal knowledge. Their work remains at the heart of what makes this journal a beacon of academic excellence.

Finally, we thank you, our esteemed readers, for your continued engagement with the BASUG Law Journal. It is through your readership that this publication finds purpose, and we hope that this issue serves as both a valuable resource and a source of inspiration for future legal thought and action.

Sincerely,

Prof. S. M. G Kanam
Chairman of Editorial Board and Dean
Faculty of Law,
Sa'adu Zungur University

TAX AMNESTY AND TAX ADMINISTRATION IN NIGERIA: ISSUES, CHALLENGES AND PROSPECTS

By

Ibome Habila Bulmen¹ Habila Isah Barau²

Abstract

Despite numerous tax amnesty programs implemented in Nigeria, the country continues to face significant challenges in achieving voluntary tax compliance, resulting in substantial revenue losses and undermining the nation's economic development. The ineffective implementation of tax amnesty programs is attributed to various factors, including: Lack of clear guidelines and regulations, inadequate public awareness and education, insufficient incentives for taxpayers to participate, Weak institutional framework and capacity, Corruption, and lack of transparency. These challenges hinder the effectiveness of tax amnesty programs, leading to low participation rates, limited revenue generated, and a persistent culture of tax evasion and avoidance. This paper examined the concept of tax amnesty and its impact on tax administration in Nigeria, highlighting the challenges and prospects of implementing tax amnesty programmes in Nigeria. The Nigerian tax administration faces numerous challenges which including globalization and profit shifting, which have resulted in significant revenue losses for the government. The study adopts a conceptual approach, reviewing existing literature on tax amnesty and tax administration. The paper identifies the weakness and challenges faced by the Nigerian tax system which include lack of clarity on tax jurisdiction and the inability to track hidden income. It also highlights the need for a critical assessment of the Nigerian tax information policy to withstand global trends in international taxation and concludes that tax amnesty programmes can be an effective tool for improving tax compliance and generating revenue for the government. The paper adopts a doctrinal method were books, case laws and other materials will be examined. Among the findings made in the paper are; there is no focused and sustained implementation of the National Tax Policy by relevant agencies to achieve its set goals and objectives, the tax legislations have become obsolete to reflect the new policy direction, the tax authorities were weak and their functions were taking over by consultants be strengthened by improving their man power and capacity towards adopting standard practices in tax administration, and the recommends among other things that there should be a focused and sustained implementation of the National Tax Policy by relevant agencies to achieve its set goals and objectives, there should also be a review of tax legislations which have become obsolete to reflect the new policy direction, and the tax authorities should be strengthened by improving their man power and capacity towards adopting standard practices in tax administration.

Keywords: Tax, Tax Amnesty, Tax Administration

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1.0 Introduction

Nigeria is a Federation which comprises of federal, state and local governments. In this federation, there are 36 states and the Federal Capital Territory with 774 Local Governments. The Country also operates a fiscal federalism which implies that each tier of government has its taxing powers which makes it possible for the various tiers to have their tax authorities. At the federal level, the tax authority is the Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS), the states have their Internal Revenue Service, while the Local governments have their Revenue Committees.³

In order to vigorously pursue the tax policy in Nigeria, various laws have been enacted to achieve these goals. These laws include the Personal Income Tax Act (PITA), Companies Income Tax Act (CITA), Capital Gains Tax Act (CGTA), Petroleum Profit Tax Act, Stamp Duties Act, among others. These statutes and even the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999 (as amended) serve as sources of tax laws in the country.⁴

It is a known fact that no country has been able to come up with a foolproof tax system that covers all areas effectively. Therefore, the Nigerian tax system is not bereft of its challenges. For instance, scholars have argued that the tax system favours the federal government over other tiers of government.⁵ Other challenges include multiple taxation, jurisdictional issues as to which tax authority to administer Value Added Tax, an inadequate database base, and the good old issue of corruption in the system.

One of the many functions of taxation is to generate revenue for the government. This has usually served as a major source of income for many countries. Countries like the United Kingdom depend solely on taxation for revenue. In Nigeria, the major source of income for government has been revenue generated from the oil and gas industry. However, with the recent down turn in the global oil market and subsequent decline in oil revenue, government has now turned its attention to non-oil revenue as a tool for economic stability. Due to the recession which the country is presently confronted with, government now considers taxation as a veritable tool in combating the

³Personal Income Tax Act, LFN 2011 Sec 10

⁴ Asada Dominic, Lecture Notes on Law of Taxation 2023/2024 LLM class University of Jos.

⁵ibid

economic woes of the country. In order to achieve this, there is a need to grow Nigeria's tax revenue and raise non-oil tax to GDP ratio.

However, in as much as this is desirable, the economic crisis has caused the challenge for tax compliance and government demand for the support of tax payers in the face of dwindling revenue.⁶ Other challenges faced by the Nigerian Tax System include; lack of clarity on taxation powers of each level of government, insufficient information available to taxpayers on tax compliance and the literacy level of the Nigerian populace concerning tax matters, economic recession which tends to worsen tax payers compliance etc.⁷ It is our considered view that Tax amnesty can ameliorate some of these challenges and improve tax revenue.

2.0 Meaning and Significance of Tax

So many definitions have been given to explain the term tax but for the purpose of this paper, we shall adopt two definitions. The first definition of the term tax connotes a legally enforceable contribution which is levied on persons, incomes, commodities and transactions for the support of government. It may also be looked at as 'a charge imposed by governmental authority upon properties, individuals or transactions to raise money for public purposes.' As sound as these definitions may be, they are far from being perfect since tax can be imposed on a group of people, communities and families in Nigeria.⁸ It is safe to say that by nature taxes are compulsorily charged for different legitimate functions by a competent authority.⁹

Generally, tax payments serves the following purposes: To yield public revenue to enable government offer protection and other socio-economic amenities to the people; promote stable economic advancement and reduce inequalities in the distribution of

⁶ Asada D, Viability and Otherwise of Tax in a Country under Recession, A Paper presented at the 2016 NBA Jos Branch Law Week.

⁷ National Tax Policy, 2016 p2

⁸Personal Income Tax Act, LFN 2011, Section 2

⁹Abdulrazak, MT 'Principles and Practice of Nigerian Tax Planning and Management (1993), Ilorin; (Batay Law Publication Ltd.)¹; see Hopkins J., New Webster Dictionary of English Language, College Edition (India: Subject Publications 2000)¹⁵⁷⁴. Section 1 of the Personal Income Tax Act 2011.

income and wealth; to discourage hazardous and socially undesirable activities such as smoking, drinking, and to encourage persons in taxable activities.¹⁰

From the definition above, it is safe to say that tax has the following features:

- a. Tax is an imposition by government.
- b. The payment of tax is compulsory and not voluntary.
- c. It as an imposition made for the general public's good and purpose. The application of the revenue depends on the policy and priorities of government at a time.¹¹

3.0 Tax Administration Challenges in Nigeria

In Nigeria, the tax system is administered by tax authorities at the different tiers of government as established by various laws. These organs and agencies are in charge of the tax policy implementation in Nigeria. They are held responsible for assessing, collecting and administering tax processes.¹²

Interestingly, it has been noted that tax administration is complex. Considering the federal system of government practiced, with its attendant three tiers, that is, the federal, state and local governments, tax organs are replicated among these tiers. This has led to the creation of the Joint Tax Board (JTB) with a mandate as an arbitrating body to mediate in issues surrounding various states. Some of the challenges are outlined here under.

3.1 Multiple Taxation

Due to the multiple tax organs, issues of multiple taxation have been on the increase. This has not only become a cancerous leach in the body of corporate entities but has also constituted a major source of revenue leakage as illegal agents have taken advantage of the situation to exploit unsuspecting tax payers. This also constitutes an unhealthy development in the tax system. It drives up the cost of production,

¹⁰Such as the provision for tax incentives. Tax can be a flexible and potential instrument for the achievement of specific economic objectives of government.

¹¹Asada Dominic, Lecture Notes on Law of Taxation 2023/2024 LLM class University of Jos.

¹²Zakariya G, Tax Administration Problems and Prospect: A Case study of Gombe State. www.ijac.org.uk> 16.-187-196.pdf accessed 17 March, 2025

encourages tax evasion and extinction of businesses.¹³ This problem has remained a hydra-headed monster which has continued to bedevil the tax system.

Consequently, this necessitated the enactment of the Taxes and Levies Act, 1998,¹⁴ which was aimed at making a clear distinction between taxes collectable by the various levels of government. By virtue of this Act, the Federal Government is empowered to administer eight (8) types of taxes which include; the Petroleum Profit Tax, the Companies Income Tax, Stamp Duties, Capital Gains Tax, Personal Income Tax and the Value Added Tax¹⁵. States have authority on taxes such as, Personal Income tax, Stamp Duties, Capital gains Tax etc.¹⁶ while the Local Governments were allocated seventeen (17) items in total which includes Collection of Rates Radio and Television licenses, Collection of revenue from Restaurants, Bakeries and other places of sale of food to the public, Licensing Regulation and Control for the sale of liquor and collection of Rates from Markets and Motor Parks¹⁷ to mention a few.

In spite of this clear cut distinctions, multiple taxation has persisted and even Court orders such as in **Mobil Producing (Nig) Unltd V. Tai Local Government Council & 2 Ors.**¹⁸ and **Etiosa Local Government Area V. Jegede**¹⁹ respectively, where the issue of multiplicity of taxes were separately raised, the courts noted in respect of the former that the local government powers to levy taxes are limited to items on Part III of the Act, while in the latter case, it also held that local governments cannot impose tax outside the items contained in Part III of the Act.

It is important to note that the 1999 Constitution clearly provides the guidelines for ascertaining the scope of the area of competence of the various levels of government, while Section 10 of the Taxes and Levies Act unambiguously states that the federal, state and local government shall be responsible for collecting taxes and levies, embodied in part I, II and III respectively. But practical application or interpretation

¹³ Asada Dominic, lecture notes on law of Taxation 2023/2024 LLM class University of Jos.

¹⁴ Decree No. 21, 1998

¹⁵ Schedule Part I, Taxes and Levies (Approved List for Collection) Act.

¹⁶ Part II, Ibid

¹⁷Fourth schedule to the 1999 constitution of Nigeria (as Amended).

¹⁸ (2003) 18 NWLR (Pt. 852)346

¹⁹(2007) 10NWLR (pt. 1043)537

by tax authorities has remained an impracticable task. The Joint Tax Board needs to be more proactive in stemming the tide of inappropriate collection of taxes. The introduction of online electronic payment of tax by the Joint Tax Board was directed at solving the problem of multiple taxation.

3.2 Insufficient Information on Tax Compliance Requirement

Another major challenge of tax administration is the problem of insufficient information available to taxpayers on tax compliance requirements²⁰. Having a largely illiterate populace, tax authorities need to do a lot more to educate taxable persons on their obligations to the government via tax. They need to understand that these taxes are essential for providing public services such as maintenance of National security, good road networks, good health care system, housing and education which are necessary for the social and economic wellbeing of the citizens. A large percentage of small business owners are illiterates who do not comprehend the tax system. Even where they know that there is an obligation on them to pay their taxes; they do not know the appropriate tax authority to whom to fulfill this obligation. This has led to them falling prey to unscrupulous touts who have taken advantage of the situation to swindle these small businesses of their hard-earned money.

3.3 Inadequate Data on Taxable Persons

The third issue is the problem of inadequate data on taxable persons. This problem seems to cut across virtually all aspects of the Nigerian Society. The government has been unable to successfully come up with an efficient data capturing mechanism. It is thus no different with the tax system. Tax authorities have failed woefully in their bid to gather up data on taxable persons in the informal sector. There is no record on the number of taxable persons in the informal sector. This has resulted in massive loss of revenue to taxable persons who are not captured within the tax net.

Worse still, even for those who have been captured within the tax net, no mechanism has been put in place to ensure adequate assessment of such persons. This has paved way for inadequate taxation. Tax authorities are left at the mercy of those persons to provide details of their income whether rightly or wrongly.

²⁰National Tax Policy, 2016 p.2

3.4 Inadequate Enforcement of Tax Laws

There is also the issue of inadequate enforcement of relevant tax laws, which has contributed immensely to the challenges bedeviling tax administration in Nigeria. A lot of persons have found it very easy to evade tax because of inadequate enforcement of tax codes in the country. The enforcement units of most of the tax authorities suffer from inadequate manpower, hence, enforcement has been porous. Historically, enforcement of tax codes have been seen to be more effective when traditional rulers were used as tax collection agents. With these traditional rulers in place, enforcement was brought down to the community level and it expedited tax collection with much ease.

3.5 Inadequate Enforcement of Sanctions

Also, rarely have sanctions been meted out against defaulting tax payers. Only a pocket of tax default cases is seen in our courts. No one will deny that penal sanctions have served as deterrence to other prospective defaulters in criminal administration. But this deterrent factor has been seldom employed by the tax authorities.

It is on record that the Federal High Court, as we presently had was first created as a Federal Revenue Court to try issues surrounding tax administration. This power is still retained even with the subsequent change in nomenclature of the Court and consequent enlargement of the Court's jurisdiction²¹. Yet, enforcement has left much to be desired. Tax default even in our clime is not treated as a crime. Most of the matters concerning taxation are adjudicated upon by the Tax Appeal Tribunal which has no criminal jurisdiction. Decisions of the Federal High Court have undermined the Tax Appeal Tribunal and have brought its constitutionality into question. In the cases of **TSKJ II Construces V. FIRS**²² AND **NNPC V. Tax Appeal Tribunal**²³ the courts held that the jurisdiction of the Tax Appeal Tribunal is in a collision course with the exclusive jurisdiction of the Federal High Court. These judgements have grossly undermined tax enforcement and have put the tax authorities in a bad light.

²¹ Sec. 251 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999 (as Amended)

²² Suit No. FHC/ABJ/TA/11/12

²³ Suit No. FHC/L/CS/360/2013

Other challenges adversely affecting tax administration in Nigeria are as follows;

- a. The need to grow internally generated revenue (IGR) which has led to the arbitrary exercise of taxing powers.
- b. Poor accountability for tax revenue.
- c. Insufficient capacity which has led to the delegation of taxing power to third parties, thereby creating complications in the tax system.
- d. Use of aggressive and unorthodox methods for tax collection.
- e. Failure by tax authorities to honour tax refund obligations to taxpayers.
- f. The non-regular review of tax legislations, which has led to obsolete laws
- g. Lack of strict adherence to tax policy direction and procedural guidelines for the operation of the various tax authorities.²⁴

These are in no way exhaustive of the challenges of tax administration in Nigeria, but are the most prominent.

4.0 Tax Amnesty as Panacea to Tax Evasion in Nigeria

As earlier stated, the major source of revenue in Nigeria is revenue from the oil sector. This sector accounts for about 70% of the total revenue earnings of the country. Therefore, any fall in the price of crude affects the earnings of the country and invariably the economy at large. As such, the drastic fall in the price of crude in the international market has led to a lot of economic challenges in the country and in fact brought the economy to its knees. This has led to an economic recession which the country is still battling its way out. To this end, professionals are agreed on the fact that the non-oil sector and harnessing tax opportunities will greatly aid in coming out of this recession. While the recession is blamed solely on the fall of crude prices, an inefficient tax system leading to tax avoidance and even outright evasion has re-ordered compliance level and ultimately reduced revenue generation capacity of the country. It is believed therefore, that tax amnesty could be a means of improving the revenue generation capacity of the country.

²⁴ National Tax Policy, 2016 page 2

Amnesty in its generic form refers to a legal forgiveness from certain infractions.²⁵ Tax amnesty means a form of a waiver or reduction and sometimes removal of penalties in back taxes to encourage defaulting taxpayers to pay what they owe within a specific window. This program can be designed to cover all tax payers and all types of taxes²⁶. It may also relate to waiver of all or any of the following: penalties, tax liabilities or even criminal liability. In the alternative, the amnesty can be in form of a repayment arrangement under which interests and penalties are forgone or assessed less than the prevailing market rates. The major objective of tax amnesty is to pardon or negotiate the tax liabilities of defaulting tax payers in line with the laid down statutes. It is also intended to regularize the tax affairs of persons who have defaulted in meeting their tax liabilities. This aids in improving tax compliance and widens the tax net. It is further designed to aid in raising revenue in the short term.

This is not an entirely new concept because the tax codes have employed the use of words like “tax remission” and “compounding an offence” to refer to the tax amnesty policy. However, those provisions have never been implemented. For instance, in 2024, the Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS) set a target of N4.9 trillion, but by the first quarter, key revenue-generating agencies of the federal government had failed to meet their revenue targets, resulting in a shortfall of about N916.3 billion.

This has become a recurring decimal, and tax authorities are now exploring new concepts in order to curtail such shortfalls. The FIRS last year announced the opening of a window, which would waive off penalties and interest charges for tax defaulters between 2013 and 2015. The new national tax policy as approved by the federal executive council also states that;

“Tax Authorities shall establish an administrative framework for amnesty and whistleblowing as part of strategies for curbing evasion and widening the tax net.”²⁷

This is an excellent step that should be emulated by other tiers of government so as to improve revenue and end the recession. The agency announced that the response was

²⁵ The Guardian Newspaper, Akintola W Monday 17th October 2016 <http://www2.deloitte.com/ng/en/pages/tax/articles/inside-tax-articles/amnesty-for-tax-defaulters.html>> accessed 14 March 2025

²⁶ *ibid*

²⁷ See paragraph xiv page 10, National Tax Policy

commendable. While this project is laudable, it must be noted that the window only lasted for 45 days. Also, the window was only open for small and medium-scale business owners. In the future, given the success recorded, the window should be longer, and there is a need to incorporate other business owners as well.²⁸.

Against this backdrop, recently, the national economic council granted approval in principle to the Voluntary Asset and Income Declaration Scheme (VAIDS), subject to the finalization of a broader framework. This scheme has as its objective to encourage voluntary declaration of undisclosed income and assets with consequential payment of applicable tax liabilities over a certain period. While being an opportunity for tax defaulters, the scheme is expected to generate revenue and to encourage investment and economic activities. The scheme commenced on the 1st of May, 2017, covering all taxes collectable by the state and federal government. The window period is for all back duty taxes with no limitation, and taxpayers who subscribed to the scheme will be allowed a maximum of three years within which to spread the payments. Also, this is intended to capture all classes of tax payers. Considering the success recorded within the last window, it is expected the present scheme will be of massive success, bearing in mind that it covers a longer timeframe and encompasses all taxpayers²⁹.

4.1 A cursory Analysis of the New National Tax Policy

As previously discussed in this paper, a robust and vibrant tax system is a key tool for an improved economy. Thus, the need for the development of a comprehensive tax system cannot be over-emphasized. This has become more necessary considering the dwindling resources of the country and the ever growing need to make ends meet. It is this necessity that has mandated the federal government to come up with a new policy direction for the nation's all important tax system. To this end, the Federal Executive Council approved the establishment of a new National Tax Policy. The new policy, it is expected to drive the new direction of government and also be the major policy thrust of government with regard to taxation.

²⁸1. Nigeria Considers New Tax Amnesty Framework through VAIDS <https://www.google.com.ng/url?sa=t&source=web&rct=j&url=https://www.proshareng.com/news/TAXATION/TAX-ALERT-Nigeria-considers-News-Tax-Amnesty-Framework-through-VAIDS/www.pcnigeria.com>> accessed 15 March 2025

²⁹ibid

The National Tax Policy establishes fundamental principles to guide an orderly development of the Nigerian tax system and reinforces the need for tax laws and administrative practices to promote economic development. It is imperative to note that most of the systematic and institutional problems faced by the country is not inadequate policy making but inadequate implementation. This was observed by the Minister of Finance, when she remarked that, “*Despite the existence of National Tax Policy (NTP) since 2012, it would appear that most of the key stakeholders are not sufficiently aware of its provisions resulting in its non-implementation...³⁰*” this remark is an indictment on the tax authorities who are saddled with the responsibility of enforcing tax laws and on the whole, driving the tax system to accomplish set goals and targets. To appreciate the viability and workability of the new framework, there is a need to analyze same.

The National Tax Policy (NTP) 2016 is expected to achieve the following objectives;

- a. Guide the operation and review of the tax system.
- b. Provide the basis for future tax legislation and administration.
- c. Serve as a point of reference for all stakeholders on taxation.
- d. Provide benchmark on which stakeholders shall be held accountable.
- e. Provide clarity on the roles and responsibilities of stakeholders in the tax system³¹.

From the foregoing objectives, one can see that the tax policy is framed and geared towards a future overhaul of the Nigerian tax system. It is structured to serve as a spring board for reforms in tax administration which will cover areas such as tax legislation and administration. It provides clear cut roles and responsibilities of stakeholders and tries to deal with corruption in the tax system.

Furthermore, the new policy is guided by the principles of equity and fairness, simplicity, certainty and clarity, low compliance cost, low cost of administration, flexibility and sustainability. The policy is also designed to solve the myriads of problems facing the Nigerian tax system. Specifically, it is designed to address the following;

³⁰ Page iii, Foreword to the 2016 National Tax Policy

³¹Ibid

1. Multiplicity of taxes and tax agencies.
2. Improve Nigeria's ranking on the global ease of paying taxes index from the current 181 out of 189 economies to top 50 by the year 2020.
3. Reduce income tax rates and compliance for Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises.
4. Encourage diversification, expand the country's tax base and improve Tax to GDP ratio.³²

However, to deal with the implementation problems that have plagued the Country's previous policies, unprecedented implementation measures have also been made part of the policy. The policy posits that effective implementation is crucial to the attainment of the set goals and derive maximum benefit. The implementation measures are a framework to ensure, guide and monitor implementation. This covers the following areas;

- i. Establishment of a National Tax Policy Implementation Committee.
- ii. Government to work towards ensuring that there is only one revenue Agency per tier of government.
- iii. Establishment of an Office of Tax Simplification.
- iv. A reporting framework where heads of MDAs shall give periodic reports on the level of implementation.
- v. Tax authorities to develop key performance indices for Nigeria to attain a top 50 position on the global ease of paying taxes index by 2020 and consistently improve on the ranking.
- vi. Establishment of taxation committees in all legislative houses to focus on tax matters and also monitor implementation of the policy.
- vii. To promote tax awareness and a tax culture in Nigeria.
- viii. Tax authorities to establish a framework for tax amnesty and whistle blowing.
- ix. There shall also be an Establishment Act for the Joint Tax Board (JTB) towards strengthening and repositioning it to contribute to the development of a viable tax system.

³²Taiwo O, Nigeria's New National Tax Policy: A New Dawn or Another False Start?<https://www.google.com.ng/url?sa=t&source=web&rct=j&url=https://pwnigeria.typepad.com/tax-matters-nigeria/2016/10/firs-declares-tax-amnesty-.>> accessed 7 February 2025

- x. Ministry of Finance in conjunction with the Federal Ministry of Justice shall sponsor a bill for the establishment of Tax Court as an independent body to adjudicate in tax matters.
- xi. The qualification for the lower income tax rate applicable to small businesses should be reviewed in line with current economic realities.
- xii. There shall be a minimum threshold for VAT registration in order to protect micro-businesses.³³

With this robust outlay of policy guidelines, objectives and implementation measures and if properly implemented, the policy will lead to a significant improvement in the Nigerian Tax system. The policy is simple, in plain language and concise. It is devoid of technical jargons and eases comprehension. It will further lead to strengthening of tax institutions and hopefully achieve a lot in the reform of our tax system.

5.0 Conclusion

There is no gainsaying the fact that taxation is a veritable tool for the economic development of any nation. The need to have an efficient and people friendly tax system can also not be overemphasized. Tax administration is very crucial for any economic development of a nation. However, this important tool is facing a lot of problems which requires the attention of policy makers. It is remarkable that in recent times, due to the economic recession facing the country, stakeholders have risen from their slumber and are now giving due consideration to the tax system. The revised National Tax Policy is a step in the right direction. The introduction of tax amnesty in the policy is also heartwarming. Policy makers have now seen the need to attract compliance by using incentives which will aid tax payers in meeting their obligations. It is therefore expected that efforts will now be focused on the implementation of the tax policy so as to achieve maximum benefits accruing therefrom. I am optimistic that concerted efforts towards that purpose will invariably produce desired results.

6.0 Findings

At the conclusion of this paper, the following findings were made:

³³ Ibid

1. There is no focused and sustainable implementation of the National Tax Policy by relevant agencies to achieve its set goals and objectives,

1. The tax legislations have become obsolete to reflect the new policy direction,
2. The tax authorities were weak and their functions were taking over by consultants to be strengthened by improving their man power and capacity towards adopting standard practices in tax administration,
3. There is no framework in place to assist taxpayers through enforcing tax refund, rendering free tax services, implementing tax amnesties and other measures to ensure compliance,
4. There is no strict sanctions imposed as penalties for taxpayers who are in default and also tax officials who engage in corruption, and
5. There is no mechanism of a reward for hardworking tax officials and taxpayers should be developed in order to encourage compliance.

7. o Recommendations

Having discussed some of the challenges bedeviling the tax system regarding tax amnesty and tax administration, it is only proper to close this paper by proffering solutions to those challenges as follows:

1. There should be a focused and sustained implementation of the National Tax Policy by relevant agencies to achieve its set goals and objectives,
6. There should also be a review of tax legislations which have become obsolete to reflect the new policy direction,
7. The tax authorities should be strengthened by improving their man power and capacity towards adopting standard practices in tax administration,
8. There should be a framework in place to assist taxpayers through enforcing tax refund, rendering free tax services, implementing tax amnesties and other measures to ensure compliance.
9. Strict sanctions should be imposed as penalties for taxpayers who are in default and also tax officials who engage in corruption.

A mechanism of a reward for hardworking tax officials and taxpayers should be developed in order to encourage compliance.